

Challenges And Measures to Improve Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in Management of Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

¹ Dr. Okafor Patrick Chinenye, ² Nnebedum, Chidi (Ph.D), & ³ Oshia, Eucharia Chinwe (Ph.D)

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria

^{2,3}Department of Educational Management and Policy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated challenges and measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 269 principals in the 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. All the 269 principals were used for the study due to the relatively manageable size of the population. The researchers-developed instrument titled “Challenges and Measures to improve Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in Management (CMUAIMQ) was used for data collection. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach alpha which yielded coefficients of 0.82. The researchers together with three research assistants collected data for the study using direct administration. Out of 269 copies administered, 258 copies representing 96% were successfully completed, retrieved and were used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The results of the study revealed among others that the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State were inadequate funds for procurement of AI facilities, cost high of acquiring artificial intelligence gadgets, absence of policy that encourage the use of artificial intelligence, insufficient technical expertise among school administrators, irregular electrical supply to power AI gadgets, phobia towards the use of AI-enabled devices, tendency of AI to foster high data security breaches and shortages of information technology experts to handle artificial intelligence gadgets. It was also reported that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the Post Primary Schools Service Commission should organize annual workshop on the use of artificial intelligence gadgets for principals to improve their technical expertise on their utilization in school management.

Keywords: Challenges, Measures, Utilization, Artificial Intelligence, Management

Introduction

Education is one of the instruments for equipping students with practical skills and knowledge to engage in productive activities for their living conditions and making substantial contributions to the societal progress. It is also a veritable tool for inculcating right values, cultivate critical thinking abilities, fostering spirit of inquiries, fostering problem-solving competencies to

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bring about all-round development in individuals. Okafor, Ughamadu and Maduili (2025) opined that education is a productive vehicle for economic, socio-cultural and political development of individuals and nations. The formal education system in Nigeria is structured into basic, secondary and higher levels. Okafor and Anyanwu (2025) stated that this interconnected framework emphasizes a coherent transition between levels, particularly at the secondary stage, where foundational skills for higher education and vocational pursuits are developed.

Secondary education offers learning experience which advance the skills and knowledge acquired by learners at basic level. Adinna and Okafor (2023) maintained that secondary education is the gateway to tertiary education and essentially provides greater number of lower level manpower needed for proper economic growth and national development. Secondary education is critical stage that offers learning opportunities for students to develop their talents, explore their potentials and develop necessary life skills that gives them a chance of bright future. Ikediugwu and Ibezim (2023) noted that secondary education is the type of education which the students receive after basic education to acquire additional skills and knowledge that prepare them for higher studies in tertiary institutions. Secondary education provides more in-depth and specialized training programmes for personal growth and career readiness. The overall success of secondary education is influenced by school management.

School management is the deployment, control and optimum use of all the available resources to attain predetermined goals and objectives of educational institutions. Okonkwo (2024) defined school management as a social or interactional process involving a sequence of coordinated events such as planning, organizing, coordinating and controlling of human and material resources to achieve desired outcomes in the fastest and most efficient ways. In the same vein, Ndal (2025) described school management as the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the activities and resources within an educational institution to achieve the desired educational goals and objectives. It is the process of applying administrative principles, practices, procedures and techniques to oversee activities in such a way to bring about smooth daily operations of learning institutions. According to Okafor, Ughamadu and Maduili (2025), school management is concerned with administrative processes which include: budgeting, planning, staffing and reporting to achieve educational goals. Okafor et al further said that it is the duty of principals to ensure work activities are properly harmonized, organized, coordinated and controlled in secondary schools. School management is concerned with the planning and coordination of the efforts of members of staff to get things properly done for achievement set educational goals. The rationale for school management to ensure discipline, effective implementation of curriculum, rational resource allocation, cordial relationship among members of school community, timely dissemination of information, accurate record keeping, periodic sporting activities, prudent use of facilities and funds of educational organizations. Okafor, Ughamadu and Enwezor (2025a) posited that the management of secondary school in Nigeria rests on the shoulders of the principal.

Principal is the administrative head who plans and oversees the implementation of school programmes. Okafor et al (2025) asserted that principal is the leader, controller and custodian of both academic and extra-curricular activities of a secondary school. A principal is the chief executive officer who directs and oversees the daily activities of staff to ensure smooth operations of a secondary school. Nnebedum, Akinfolarin and Obuegbe (2018) asserted that principal is a person appointed by the appropriate authority to pilot the day-to-day affairs of the school. Continuing, Nnebedum et al asserted that the principal is entrusted with numerous responsibilities such as planning, coordinating, and managing of students, staff, facilities and school funds among others. Principals in secondary schools have different job experience.

Job experience could influence the professional development needs of principals. Job experience is accumulated specialized knowledge and skills acquired by individuals in performing official duties over a period. Okafor, Ughamadu and Enwezor (2025b) noted that job experience is the period that an individual has worked for an organization. Furthermore, Okafor et al asserted that job experience provides opportunity for staff to acquire practical knowledge and ways of discharging of their duties effectively. Wealth of experience gained by principals on-the-job could help them develop some skills and knowledge in school management. In this study, principals with less than 10 years of job experience were considered as less-experienced principals, while those with above 10 years of job experience were considered as more experienced principals. Both less-experienced and more-experienced principals can automate administrative tasks to enhance their operational efficiency through utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in school management.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is set of technological devices powered to execute a variety of functions like human beings. Some of these functions include abilities to think, see, feel, comprehend, reaction to situations, make recommendations and decisions. Ndalun (2025) defined AI as the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are designed to think, learn, reason, and make decisions. Ndalun added that AI systems are capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, language translation, and problem-solving. AI powered electronic devices are capable of planning activities, remembering events, making rational decisions and solving problems just like human beings. Dipak and Suman (2024) noted that examples of AI are Robotics, computer vision, the Internet of Things, speech recognition, biometric systems, language processing and translation, expert systems, pattern recognition among others. AI is a machine that is programmed to perform tasks that requires human aptitude and cleverness. Offor, Nwaru and Offiah (2025) described AI as a constellation of technologies that enable machines to act with higher levels of intelligence while emulating human capabilities to sense, comprehend and act. Nnamdi and Uwelegbew (2025) described AI as computer systems that mimic human intellectual functions such as perception, language comprehension, learning, reasoning, and problem-solving. Nnamdi and Uwelegbew added that AI technologies use data analysis and algorithms to carry out activities that normally need human intellect. (AI) is digital devices that have been driven to think, make prediction, recall situation, recognize images, solve problems and act like human beings.

The utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational institutions is rapidly expanding in develop and developing nations of the world. Artificial intelligence is capable of streamlining managerial activities such as record management, financial management, facilities management and management of information and human resources. Ogunode and Gregory (2025) noted that utilization of artificial intelligence in educational administration can lead to effective data analysis, rational decision making, resource optimization, effective student support and intervention, streamlined communication and enhanced security and safety among others. The utilization of AI in school management is capable of analyzing vast volumes of information to aid planning and decision making in learning institutions. Igbokwe (2023) posited that AI can automate routine administrative tasks such as scheduling, grading, and record-keeping, freeing up educators and administrators to focus on more strategic and creative tasks. Oju, Orokpo, Awa and Osha (2025) asserted that AI can streamline budgeting processes, track expenditures, predict financial requirements, and deliver real-time insights into resource allocation, ensuring more effective use of funds. Oju et al added that AI tools can enhance student personnel management by automating tasks such as attendance tracking, behavior monitoring, and identifying at-risk students early, enabling timely interventions.

Many educational institutions in developing countries in general and Anambra State in particular are yet to fully integrate AI in management of secondary schools. Okafor, Ughamadu and Enwezor (2025) noted that principals apply obsolete and conventional methods of management of public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Okafor and Anyanwu (2025) noted that there is a lack of visible AI-driven managerial and instructional practices in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Ogunode and Gregory (2025) listed the possible challenges of artificial intelligence in educational management in Nigeria as follow: bias and discrimination lack of transparency and interpretability data privacy and security breaches lack of ethical and legal guidelines lack of technical expertise and resources, unstable internet services, unstable power supply, job displacement, lack of interoperability and compatibility. It is based on these problems that the researchers determined the challenges and measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the challenges and measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to ascertain the:

1. Challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

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1. What are the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Anambra State which is one of states in south-eastern Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 269 principals in the 269 public secondary schools in Anambra State. All the 269 principals were used because the size is small and manageable. Thus, there was no sampling. The researchers-developed instrument titled “Challenges and Measures to improve Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in Management (CMUAIMQ) was used for data collection. CMUAIMQ contained 20 items and is divided into two clusters, namely clusters one and two. Cluster one which sought information on challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in school management contained 10 and cluster two which elicited information on measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management contained 10 items. The response format ranges from Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 to Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

The face validity of the instrument was ascertained by three experts who are lecturers, two in the Department of Educational Management and Policy and the other, an expert in Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Their corrections were effected in the final draft of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha method which yielded of 0.79 and 0.84 for Clusters one and two respectively with an overall coefficient of 0.82.

The researchers personally visited the public secondary schools and administered the instruments on the respondents with the help of three research assistants who are postgraduate students. A total of 269 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 258 copies representing 96% return were successfully completed and retrieved. Mean and standard deviation were used answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses. For decision on the research questions, mean rating of 2.50 or above was taken as agreement, while mean rating of below 2.50 was taken as disagreement. Standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents mean ratings. In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or greater than 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was not rejected, but if p-value is less than 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores of More-Experienced and Less-Experienced Principals on Challenges to Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in School Management

S/ N	ITEMS	More-experienced principals (n = 97)			Less-experienced principals (n =161)		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Inadequate funds for procurement of AI facilities	2.76	1.08	Agree	2.69	1.05	Agree
2	Cost high of acquiring artificial intelligence gadgets	2.65	1.08	Agree	2.73	1.09	Agree
3	Absence of policy that encourage the use of artificial intelligence	2.98	0.95	Agree	2.95	1.04	Agree
4	Insufficient technical expertise in use of AI among school administrators	2.87	1.01	Agree	2.85	1.00	Agree
5	Irregular electrical supply to power AI gadgets	2.64	1.04	Agree	2.58	0.97	Agree
6	Phobia towards the use of AI-enabled devices	2.89	0.93	Agree	2.90	1.07	Agree
7	Tendency of AI to foster high data security breaches	2.65	1.01	Agree	2.60	1.10	Agree
8	Internal resistance by school administrators to use AI in school management	2.43	1.06	Disagree	2.48	1.02	Disagree
9	Shortages of information technology experts to handle artificial intelligence gadgets	2.67	1.01	Agree	2.63	1.12	Agree
10	Fear of job displacement through automation of tasks	2.43	0.98	Disagree	2.41	1.11	Disagree
Cluster Mean		2.70	1.02	Agree	2.68	1.06	Agree

Data presented on Table 1 show that the mean scores of both more-experienced and less-experienced principals are above the cut off mean of 2.50 for items 1-7 and 9. This reveals that the two groups of principals agreed with these items as the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in school management. The mean score of both more-experienced and less-experienced principals for items 8 and 10 are below the cut off mean scores of 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in school management. The standard deviation scores of 1.02 and 1.06 of more-experienced and less-experienced principals respectively indicating that the respondents' responses are homogeneous. The cluster mean of 2.70 for more-experienced and 2.68 for less-experienced principals are above

the cut off mean scores of 2.50 indicating there are many challenges to the utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What are the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores of More-Experienced and Less-Experienced Principals on the Measures to Improve Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in School Management

S/ N	ITEMS	More-experienced principals (n = 97)			Less-experienced principals (n =161)		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SD	Decision
11	Increase in funding of schools for procurement of AI facilities	2.93	1.06	Agree	2.91	0.95	Agree
12	Subsidizing the costs of acquiring artificial intelligence gadgets	3.04	1.10	Agree	3.15	1.07	Agree
13	Enactment of policy that encourage the use of artificial intelligence	2.87	1.04	Agree	2.90	1.11	Agree
14	Training of staff to up-date the technical expertise among school administrators	2.82	1.03	Agree	2.94	1.09	Agree
15	Improving electrical supply to power AI gadgets	2.79	1.00	Agree	2.86	1.08	Agree
16	Sensitization of administrators to reduce phobia towards the use of AI-enabled devices	2.65	0.97	Agree	2.69	1.04	Agree
17	Design of AI-enabled data surveillance to maintain privacy	2.77	1.11	Agree	2.85	1.07	Agree
18	Orientation of administrators to discourage internal resistance towards the usage of AI in school management	2.44	1.05	Disagree	2.40	1.12	Disagree
19	deployment of information technology experts in schools to handle artificial intelligence gadgets	2.64	1.04	Agree	2.70	1.05	Agree
20	Assurance of job security in the face of automation of tasks through AI	2.48	1.09	Disagree	2.41	1.01	Disagree
Cluster Mean		2.74	1.05	Agree	2.78	1.06	Agree

As shown in Table 2, the mean scores of both more-experienced and less-experienced principals are above the cut off mean of 2.50 for items 11-17 and 19. This reveals that the two groups of principals agreed with these items as the measures to improve the utilization of artificial intelligence in school management. The mean score of both more-experienced and less-experienced principals for items 18 and 20 are below the cut off mean scores of 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as the measures to improve the utilization of artificial intelligence in

school management. The standard deviation scores of 1.05 and 1.06 of more-experienced and less-experienced principals respectively indicating that the respondents' responses are homogeneous. The cluster mean of 2.74 for more-experienced and 2.78 for less-experienced principals are above the cut off mean scores of 2.50 indicating there are many measures to improve the utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: The Summary of t-test of Significant Difference Between the Mean Ratings of More-Experienced and Less-Experienced Principals on the Challenges to Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in School Management

Respondents	N	X	SD	p-value	∞	Df	Remark
More-experienced Principals	97	2.70	1.02	0.34	0.05	256	Not Significant
Less-experienced Principals	161	2.68	1.06				

Table 3 shows that the p-value of 0.34 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 256 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the groups was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: The Summary of t-test of Significant Difference Between the Mean Ratings of More-Experienced and Less-Experienced Principals on the Measures to Improve the Utilization of Artificial Intelligence in School Management

Respondents	N	X	SD	p-value	∞	Df	Remark
More-experienced Principals	97	2.74	1.05	0.28	0.05	256	Not Significant
Less-experienced Principals	161	2.78	1.06				

Result in Table 4 shows that the p-value of 0.28 is greater than 0.05 level of significance at 256 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant

difference between the groups was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The result of the study indicated that there are many challenges to the utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. The challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State were inadequate funds for procurement of AI facilities, cost high of acquiring artificial intelligence gadgets, absence of policy that encourage the use of artificial intelligence, insufficient technical expertise among school administrators, irregular electrical supply to power AI gadgets, phobia towards the use of AI-enabled devices, tendency of AI to foster high data security breaches and shortages of information technology experts to handle artificial intelligence gadgets. This is in line with the finding of Nnamdi and Uwelegbew (2025) which revealed that challenges encountered by school administrators in leveraging artificial intelligence were absence of proper infrastructure, which includes erratic power supplies and spotty internet access, inadequate funding, lack of technical expertise, data privacy and ethical concerns and digital divide. The agreement of the findings could be attributed to the low budgetary allocation and absence of AI policy in Nigeria, where the studies were conducted. It was also found that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and less-experienced principals on the challenges to utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The finding of the study revealed that there are many measures to improve the utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State. The measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State were increase in funding of schools for procurement of AI facilities, subsidizing the costs of acquiring artificial intelligence gadgets, enactment of policy that encourage the use of artificial intelligence, training of staff to up-date the technical expertise among school administrators, improving electrical supply to power AI gadgets, sensitization of administrators to reduce phobia towards the use of AI-enabled devices, design of AI-enabled data surveillance to maintain privacy and deployment of information technology experts in schools to handle artificial intelligence gadgets. This agreed with the finding of Nnamdi and Uwelegbew (2025) which showed the measures to improve the application of artificial intelligence in school administration were improved AI Infrastructure Investment, adequate funding, regular training on AI technologies and their applications in school management, formulation of Policy and Regulatory Frameworks that encourage the use of AI in school management. Further result indicated that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of more-experienced and

less-experienced principals on the measures to improve utilization of artificial intelligence in management of public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings it was concluded that the utilization of artificial intelligence in management is confronted with vast challenges public secondary schools in Anambra State. Some of these challenges are poor funding, shortage of skills, insufficient AI gadgets and absence of policy among others. These challenges have generated concerns that require improved funding and provision of AI gadgets among others.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

1. Government should increase budgetary allocation to school to enable school management procure and utilize AI gadgets in school management.
2. Post Primary Schools Service Commissions should organize annual workshop on artificial intelligence gadgets for principals to improve their technical expertise on their utilization in school management.

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